

Starbucks and MENA's Geopolitical Challenges: Prioritizing Resilience and Employee Well-being

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Abstract

This study looks at the influence of geopolitical concerns on Starbucks' operations in the MENA region, specifically through the Alshaya Group franchise. The study focuses on the Israel-Hamas conflict and related boycotts, emphasizing the relevance of resilience and employee well-being in overcoming these hurdles. It stresses measures such as promoting well-being, building resilience, and improving workplace communication. The study concludes with recommendations for future research on the long-term effects of conflicts on retail franchises, as well as the role of communication in preserving trust and resilience. This study offers valuable insights for international retail franchises operating in politically risky countries.

Keywords: Geopolitical tensions, Middle East retail market, Workforce reductions, Employee support and rehabilitation, Organizational resilience

Introduction

Alshaya Group, a Middle East and North Africa (MENA) powerhouse, has a huge impact on the region's economic landscape and is a cornerstone of the Middle East's global food and beverage industry. Alshaya has established itself as a leader in the retail franchise industry, owning about 1,900 Starbucks locations and managing approximately 70 consumer retail brands across MENA, Turkey, and Europe (Wikipedia, 2024).

However, recent developments have placed doubt on Alshaya's activities, particularly inside its Starbucks franchise. The continuing Israel-Hamas war has resulted in boycotts of Starbucks locations throughout the region, causing Alshaya Group to announce a staff cut of approximately 2,000 employees. This decision, which represents little more than 10% of the workforce, highlights Starbucks' challenging business environment in the Middle East and North Africa (CBS News, 2024). Alshaya Group, a Kuwait-based family firm, bemoaned the need for this relocation, citing ongoing hard commercial conditions compounded by geopolitical concerns. Despite the sad nature of the

decision, Alshaya thought it necessary to handle the franchisee's operating challenges in the aftermath of the ongoing crisis (Reuters, 2024).

Starbucks isn't the only Western brand affected by the Israel-Hamas conflict. McDonald's, Burger King, KFC, Pizza Hut, and other restaurants have experienced boycotts from both pro-Palestinian and pro-Israel organizations. Chris Kempczinski, CEO of McDonald's, agreed that the war had a "meaningful business impact" in the Middle East and other places. Furthermore, Starbucks has faced allegations of financial assistance for the Israeli government and military, which the firm categorically disputes on its website, emphasizing its dedication to transparency (CBS News, 2024).

Beyond the economic repercussions, the war has resulted in unsettling instances. In one case, a Starbucks in Glen Rock, New Jersey, uncovered red paint and antisemitic stickers relating to the conflict on its sign. Starbucks recently filed a lawsuit against the union Workers United for a pro-Palestinian statement posted online, showing the difficulty of navigating geopolitical tensions in the retail industry (CBS News, 2024). Beyond the economic consequences, the war has produced disquieting incidents. In one instance, a Starbucks in Glen Rock, New Jersey, discovered red paint and antisemitic stickers related to the conflict on its sign. Starbucks recently sued the union Workers United over a pro-Palestinian remark posted online, demonstrating the challenge of navigating geopolitical issues in the retail sector (CBS News, 2024).

Alshaya Group's success as an international retail franchise operator demonstrates its endurance and adaptability in the face of hardship. As the company navigates the stormy seas of the Middle Eastern retail market, it stays committed to providing consumers with unmatched experiences while dealing with geopolitical unpredictability (Arab news, 2024).

Psychological Impact of Workforce Reduction

Meanwhile, the layoff of 2000 Starbucks employees arranged by Alshaya Group in response to geopolitical developments, is a complicated challenge that goes beyond economic concerns. The section's discussion dives into the psychological effects of workforce decrease and discusses ways for reducing employee discomfort. Involuntary job loss frequently causes a variety of negative feelings and psychological suffering in those impacted (Brockner *et al.*, 1992). Employees who are abruptly terminated from their jobs may experience feelings of shock, worry, and uncertainty as they deal with the loss of financial security and professional identity. Layoffs may also exacerbate previous mental health concerns and have long-term psychological implications if not managed adequately (Fortin & Lemieux, 1997).

Many people regard their job as an essential component of their identity and self-worth. As a result, losing one's job can cause severe grief and low self-esteem (Brockner *et al.*, 1992). Individuals may struggle to reconcile their professional goals with the realities of unemployment, resulting in emotions of inadequacy and despair (Fortin & Lemieux, 1997). Layoffs can also disrupt social networks and support systems, isolating people and worsening feelings of loneliness and alienation (Brockner *et al.*, 1992).

According to research, layoffs may disproportionately affect certain demographic groups, such as elderly workers or those from underprivileged neighborhoods (Fortin & Lemieux, 1997). This exacerbates existing disparities in society and contributes to sentiments of injustice and discrimination among those affected. Furthermore, the psychological impact of job loss may be exacerbated by systemic hurdles to reemployment, sustaining cycles of poverty and social isolation (Fortin and Lemieux, 1997).

Given these psychological hurdles, firms such as Alshaya Group must emphasize employee well-being and provide comprehensive support in order to offset the negative consequences of layoffs. This involves providing counseling services, mental health resources, and career transition assistance to employees who are dealing with the emotional impact of job loss (Carroll & Shabana, 2010). Furthermore, cultivating an environment of empathy, openness, and open communication can assist employees establish trust and resilience, easing their psychological rehabilitation and reintegration into the workforce (Cameron & Green, 2019).

The psychological impact of workforce reduction is substantial and far-reaching, demanding proactive interventions to assist impacted individuals. Understanding the psychological dynamics at work and adopting focused interventions can help firms reduce employee misery and establish a supportive work environment that promotes long-term well-being and resilience.

Recommendations for Mitigating Workforce Reduction Challenges

1. Implement Organizational Resilience Strategies

Alshaya Group can offset the effects of personnel reductions by employing organizational resilience initiatives. Organizational resilience is defined as an organization's ability to adapt and thrive in the face of adversity (Linnenluecke & Griffiths, 2010). One method to accomplish this is to diversify your business operations. Alshaya can consider expanding its portfolio beyond the food and beverage sector in order to lessen dependency on a particular business. Alshaya can diversify its revenue streams and mitigate the impact of layoffs on its staff by growing into new industries like as retail, hotel, and technology (Nyaupane *et al.*, 2020).

To mitigate the impact of Starbucks employment reductions, Alshaya Group may also explore rebranding Starbucks stores under a new name while keeping the same idea and offers. This method would entail altering the branding, signage, and marketing materials to match the new name and image while retaining the current menu and customer experience. Alshaya, for example, may launch a new coffee shop brand with a distinctive and original identity that caters to local tastes and preferences. The new brand might emphasize quality, sustainability, and community engagement, drawing influence from Starbucks' core values.

Alshaya can generate excitement and intrigue among customers by rebranding Starbucks stores under a new name, while also separating the coffee shops from any negative associations associated with regional geopolitical problems. This strategy would enable Alshaya to maintain its market

presence while mitigating the impact of personnel reductions on the Starbucks brand and its employees.

2. Leverage Human Capital Management Approaches

Alshaya Group can mitigate the impact of human losses by implementing organizational resilience strategies. Organizational resilience is described as an organization's capacity to adapt and thrive in the face of adversity (Linnenluecke & Griffiths, 2010; Wijaya *et al.*, 2021). One way to do this is to diversify your business operations. Alshaya can explore diversifying its portfolio beyond the food and beverage industry in order to reduce reliance on a single firm. Alshaya can diversify its revenue streams and lessen the impact of layoffs on employees by expanding into new areas like as retail, hospitality, and technology (Nyaupane *et al.*, 2020).

To reduce the impact of Starbucks' employment reductions, Alshaya Group can implement many organizational resilience methods, with a focus on diversifying its business operations. One strategy is to look into ways to broaden its business beyond the food and beverage industry. Alshaya can diversify into new industries such as retail, hotel, and technology to lessen its dependency on a single brand, like Starbucks. Retail diversification might include purchasing or developing additional retail brands to complement Starbucks' existing locations. Alshaya, for example, might diversify its revenue streams by investing in retail chains that sell clothing, electronics, or home goods. Alshaya can mitigate the impact of Starbucks' labor reductions by expanding into retail and leveraging its existing infrastructure, knowledge, and client base.

Alshaya might also look at chances in the hospitality industry by investing in hotel chains, resorts, and other hospitality businesses. This diversification can provide a steady supply of money and job possibilities, helping to mitigate the effects of Starbucks' layoffs. Alshaya can serve to various consumer segments and increase its market resiliency by providing a variety of hospitality services. Investing in technological projects, on the other hand, can help organizations become more resilient. Alshaya can diversify its revenue streams and lessen reliance on physical retail outlets such as Starbucks by pursuing opportunities in e-commerce, software development, and digital services. Alshaya can keep up with market trends and evolving consumer preferences by adopting technological innovation.

3. Foster Employee Engagement and Well-being

Maintaining high levels of employee engagement and well-being is critical to corporate success, particularly during times of uncertainty (Saks, 2006). Alshaya can prioritize programs that promote a healthy work environment and assist its employees' physical and emotional wellbeing. This may involve creating flexible work arrangements, encouraging work-life balance, and providing access to wellness programs and counseling services (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). Alshaya can boost morale, lower absenteeism, and increase overall corporate performance by displaying a commitment to employee well-being (Kahn, 1990).

Several technical solutions might be adopted to improve employee engagement and well-being at Starbucks following Alshaya Group's layoffs. One way is to implement comprehensive staff support programs that promote physical and emotional well-being. Alshaya can implement flexible work arrangements to meet employees' personal needs and develop a better work-life balance. This could include remote work choices, flexible scheduling, or reduced workweeks to reduce stress and increase job satisfaction. Furthermore, giving access to wellness programs like gym memberships, mental health resources, and counseling services can help employees manage their overall well-being.

Furthermore, Alshaya might spend in training and development programs to improve employees' skills and competences. Offering opportunities for professional development and progress can make employees feel appreciated and invested in their professions, boosting engagement and commitment to the firm. This could include giving employees access to online classes, workshops, or mentorship programs that are suited to their interests and professional goals. Creating a culture of open communication and transparency can help to sustain staff morale and trust during times of uncertainty. Alshaya may invest in training and development programs to enhance employees' skills and competencies. Offering opportunities for professional development and advancement can make employees feel valued and invested in their careers, hence increasing engagement and commitment to the company.

This could involve providing employees with online classes, workshops, or mentorship programs tailored to their interests and professional aspirations. Creating an environment of open communication and transparency can help to maintain employee morale and trust during times of uncertainty. In addition, recognizing and praising employee efforts can increase morale and motivation in the workplace. Alshaya can put in place programs to recognize great performance, teamwork, and innovation. This could include both formal incentives like bonuses or awards, as well as more casual expressions of gratitude like customized thank-you notes or public recognition ceremonies.

4. Enhance Communication and Transparency

Open and open communication is critical for fostering trust and sustaining employee morale during times of transition (Grossman & Salas, 2011). Alshaya should publicly communicate with employees about the reasons for the layoffs, the company's future objectives, and the resources accessible to affected employees. Alshaya can assist ease employee uncertainty and anxiety while also fostering a sense of trust and devotion to the firm (Kotter, 2012).

Several technical techniques might be applied at Starbucks to improve communication and openness in the aftermath of Alshaya Group's layoffs. First, Alshaya should develop clear and open lines of communication to keep employees informed about the reasons for the layoffs, the company's future goals, and the services accessible to affected employees. This could include regular updates via email, company-wide meetings, intranet portals, and corporate newsletters. Transparent communication about the decision-making process and the company's plans can help to reduce employee uncertainty and anxiety, creating trust and confidence in the organization's leadership.

Alshaya should also encourage two-way communication by giving staff opportunities to express their issues, ask questions, and provide feedback. This could involve holding open forums, town hall meetings, or virtual Q&A sessions in which employees can express themselves and receive feedback from management. Implementing anonymous suggestion boxes or online feedback platforms can also allow employees to submit their ideas and concerns in a confidential manner, promoting honest and productive communication.

In addition, Alshaya should teach managers and leaders how to interact effectively with their teams, emphasizing empathy, active listening, and openness. Managers should have the expertise and tools to address employee issues, offer support, and foster open communication among their teams. Regular check-ins and one-on-one meetings allow managers to interact with employees personally, understand their needs, and provide individualized support during times of transition. Alshaya ought to utilize technology to improve communication and transparency, especially in distant or distributed work contexts.

Implementing collaboration technologies such as video conferencing platforms, instant messaging apps, and project management software allows employees to communicate and collaborate in real-time, regardless of their location. This can help to preserve a sense of closeness and camaraderie in the workplace, regardless of physical distance. Alshaya can effectively support Starbucks employees throughout the difficult moment of layoffs by using technical strategies to improve communication and transparency, promoting trust, engagement, and resilience inside the organization. This proactive strategy not only boosts employee morale and loyalty, but also promotes a great workplace culture and long-term business success.

Conclusion

Alshaya Group's supremacy in the MENA retail franchise industry is clear, however recent obstacles caused by the Israel-Hamas war have hampered its Starbucks franchise and resulted in labor layoffs. These incidents show the challenges of operating in the Middle Eastern retail industry while geopolitical tensions persist. To successfully traverse these issues, Alshaya Group must emphasize employee well-being, adopt organizational resilience methods, encourage engagement and well-being, and improve communication. Furthermore, by undertaking this, the organization may be able to mitigate the negative effects of layoffs while simultaneously maintaining a supportive work environment for future growth.

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